

STUDIES ON THE FRIES REARRANGEMENT. PART V

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Fries rearrangement of various substituted phenolic esters of crotonic acid has been studied.

In continuation of our work on Fries rearrangement (Sen and Misra, this *Journal*, 1949, 26, 339) we have now extended the work to ten more phenolic esters of crotonic acid. The rearrangement was carried out in the usual way in the presence of carbon disulphide using 1.2 to 1.3 moles of anhydrous aluminium chloride. In all the cases only *o*-hydroxy-ketones were obtained in yields ranging from 31 to 86 %. These ketones have been characterised through their 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazones.

EXPERIMENTAL

Crotonyl chloride was prepared by following the method of Staudinger *et al.* (*Escr.*, 1916, 49, 1991), b. p. 123°—125° (Staudinger *et al.* report b. p. 124°-126°).

Phenolic Esters of Crotonic Acid.—0.1 Mole of phenol in 20-25 c.c. of anhydrous-benzene was taken in a round bottomed flask fitted with a reflux condenser containing a calcium chloride tube. To this clean and dry magnesium ribbon in the form of a spiral was added (catalyst). Now 0.1 mole of crotonyl chloride was gradually added through a dropping funnel. The mixture was refluxed on the water-bath till hydrogen chloride had ceased to evolve. The completion of the reaction took nearly 10-12 hours ; after cooling water was added and the benzene layer separated. It was then washed with 1% caustic soda solution and finally with water. The benzene extract was dried over anhydrous calcium chloride and the benzene removed by distillation. The residual oil was distilled under reduced pressure, yield 58-96.8%.

The esters thus obtained are summarised in Table I.

Fries Rearrangement of the Esters.—The appropriate ester (0.053 mole) was taken in a 500 c. c. round bottomed flask fitted with a reflux condenser and a calcium chloride guard tube. To this 15 c. c. of carbon disulphide and then 0.079 mole of finely powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride were added to it and the mixture was refluxed on the water-bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour ; subsequently the carbon disulphide distilled off. The residual mass was then heated in an oil-bath at 120° for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. On decomposing the resultant puffy mass with ice and dilute hydrochloric acid an oil separated out (solids in the case of three esters, which were filtered and recrystallised from hot alcohol). It was taken

TABLE I

No.	Phenol.	Crotonyl chloride.	B. P.	Esters yield.	Mol. formula	Found		Calc.	
						C.	H.	C.	H.
1.	<i>m</i> -Ethylphenol	10.5 g.	I. 135°/14mm.	58.0%	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₂	75.08%	6.77%	75.78%	7.37%
2.	5-Hydroxy-1:3-dimethylbenzene	10.5	II. 166°/13mm.	61.0	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₂	75.15	6.85	75.78	7.37
3.	1:3:5-Ethylmethylphenol	10.5	III. 162°/11mm.	62.8	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ O ₂	75.79	8.54	76.47	7.84
4.	1:4:5-Xylenol	12.9	IV. 139°-141°/23mm.	87.4	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₂	75.15	7.95	75.78	7.37
5.	1:3:4-Xylenol	12.9	V. 150°/3mm.	71.0	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₂	75.11	7.82	75.78	7.37
6.	<i>p</i> - <i>tert</i> -Butylphenol	13.0	VI. 156°/3mm.	68.8	C ₁₄ H ₁₈ O ₂	76.44	8.73	77.05	8.26
7.	<i>p</i> - <i>tert</i> -Amylphenol	14.96	VII. 158°/3mm.	62.5	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ O ₂	77.08	9.21	77.59	8.62
8.	Guaiacol	11.9	VIII. 145°/5mm.	70.2	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ O ₂	68.13	6.05	68.74	6.25
9.	Hydroquinone monomethyl ether	14.3	IX. 152°/2mm.	96.8	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ O ₂	68.06	6.35	68.74	6.25
10.	Resorcinol monomethyl ether	11.5	X. 133°/3mm.	76.7	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ O ₂	68.03	6.74	68.74	6.25

up in ether, washed successively with water, 1% sodium carbonate solution and finally with water. The ethereal layer was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the ether removed by distillation. The residual oil was distilled under reduced pressure. The hydroxy-ketones obtained conformed to Pyman's test (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 280) for *o*-hydroxy-ketones.

TABLE II

Products of the Fries rearrangement of the esters.

No.	Ester.	AlCl ₃ .	Hydroxy-ketone		2:4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone.		Nitrogen	
			B. P. & M. P.	Yield	M. P.	Mol. formula.	Found.	Calc.
I.	6.0 g.	6.4 g.	183°/20mm.	76.7 %	243°	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₅ N ₄	14.61 %	15.14 g.
II.	7.0	7.5	143°/20mm.	78.6	187°	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₅ N ₄	14.65	15.14
III.	8.0	7.9	144°/1mm.	57.5	229°	C ₁₀ H ₂₀ O ₅ N ₄	14.12	14.58
IV.	10.0	10.6	161°	53.0	243°	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₅ N ₄	14.65	15.14
V.	10.0	10.6	142°/2mm.	86.0	249°	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₅ N ₄	14.69	15.14
VI.	10.0	9.3	115°/5mm.	31.0	236°	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ O ₅ N ₄	13.81	14.07
VII.	10.0	8.7	114°/3mm.	58.0	179°	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₅ N ₄	13.06	13.59
VIII.	10.0	10.5	103°/2mm.	32.0	155°	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₅ N ₄	14.63	15.06
IX.	10.0	10.5	88°	54.0	...	...	...	...
X.	10.0	10.5	84°	42.0	238°	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₅ N ₄	14.48	15.06

These ketones obtained were all converted into 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazones which were recrystallised from hot glacial acetic acid except in the case of *o*-hydroxy-ketone No. IX, the 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone could not be prepared. The *o*-hydroxy-ketone No. IX gave on analysis: C, 68.3; H, 6.18; C₁₁H₁₀O₅ requires C, 68.74; H, 6.25 per cent.

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